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FEATURES OF BASKETBALL AS A MEANS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AT THE UNIVERSITY

Annotation. The article discusses the features of basketball as a means of physical education at the university.

Keywords. Sports games, physical education, physical development, movement, sports, games.

Basketball attracts with its entertainment, an abundance of various technical and tactical techniques, emotionality, lightness, dynamism, collectivism and individualism at the same time, and besides, in my opinion, and many specialists, is the most effective means for comprehensive physical development.

By the way, basketball is probably the only popular sport whose date and place of origin are known for certain. More than a dozen books have been written about this significant event, often with fictional details telling about the first steps of this future addiction of millions. And, nevertheless, it seems to me that in this manual it makes sense to outline at least schematically the main points of the formation and development of basketball, an artificially invented game that managed to win the hearts of fans all over the world in a matter of decades, which in itself seems to be an unprecedented phenomenon.

The popularity of basketball and its wide application in the system of physical education are caused, first of all, by the economic accessibility of the game, high emotionality, a great spectacular effect, a complex effect on the body and the upbringing of young people, and therefore further along the text I give the most characteristic features of basketball.

Basketball is based on natural movements - running, jumping, throwing, passing. They are easy to teach children, teenagers and adults. Therefore, basketball is included in the program of education and training of children, starting from kindergartens, and ball games - from the age of two. The desire to surpass the opponent in the speed of actions aimed at achieving victory teaches those involved to mobilize their capabilities, to act with maximum effort, to overcome difficulties arising during wrestling. These features contribute to the education of perseverance, determination and purposefulness.

The game environment changes very quickly and creates new game situations. These conditions teach players to constantly monitor the game process, instantly assess the situation, act proactively, resourcefully and quickly in any situation. Continuous observation of the game process helps the development of

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abilities for a wide distribution and concentration of attention, spatial and temporal orientation.

The competitive nature of the game, the continuous change of the situation, luck or failure causes athletes to manifest a variety of feelings and experiences that affect their activities. A high emotional level helps to maintain constant activity and interest in the game. These features of basketball create favorable conditions for the education of basketball players, the ability to manage emotions, not to lose control over their actions. This feature is of the greatest importance for fostering friendship and camaraderie, and developing the habit of subordinating their actions to the interests of the team. Basketball has become widespread all over the world, interest in this sport is increasing every year, competition in the international arena is increasing. The latter makes it necessary to improve the methods of sports training, taking into account the trends in the development of basketball.

The study of the motor and informative activity of the body, which are crucial in the implementation of skills in basketball, the conditionality of these activities with a common functional background, the integration of these factors into a single functional system to ensure high reliability of throwing the ball into the basket should have wide access to practice both in terms of methodological recommendations for improving sports skills and for testing functional readiness athletes.

The essence of the game is that the players of each team move around the court with or without the ball and, overcoming the opponent's resistance, try to throw balls into the opponent's basket as much as possible and prevent them from mastering the ball and throwing into the basket. The ball can be passed to lead, throw, hit, observing the rules of the game. The team that has more points on its account after the end of the game wins.

In basketball, the success of a team ensures an accurate finishing throw. Until recently, and even today, the main means of attack is a one-handed throw from above in a jump. In the competitions of the strongest men's teams in the world, up to 70% of all shots from the game are made in this way, from various distances.

V.G. Lunichkin to determine the most appropriate division of the throwing technique into phases and to identify patterns of variability and time stability of individual phases of the throw used a complex technique that allows recording the time characteristics of the phases of technical reception:

- 1) the moment of receiving and releasing the ball (finger contacts)
- 2) the beginning of the working phase of the movement;
- 3) the flight time of the ball (from the moment the ball is released to the touch of the ring, shield).

The author also studied the changes in the height of the jump depending on the conditions of the throw. It turned out that the height of the jump varies

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depending on the conditions of the throw. This is due to the fact that there is an adaptive correction of the motor system.

A.S. Belov recommends using such combinations of tasks in the training process to improve the effectiveness of basketball players' basket throws and the development of variability of motor skills:

The current trend of the game determines the direction of technical training. High results can be achieved only with a high level of technical readiness of the players. To do this, a basketball player must:

1) know the techniques of the game known to modern basketball and be able to implement them in different conditions;

2) be able to combine techniques with each other in any sequence in a variety of game conditions. Variety of actions, combining different techniques in a single combat with the enemy;

3) own a set of techniques that you have to use more often in the game, and perform them with the greatest effect;

2) alternating throws from a distance of 1.5 and 6 meters;

3) alternation of throws and directions perpendicular and parallel to the plane of the shield.

S. V. Golomazov, studying the trajectory of the ball and the mechanisms of controlling the movements of the basketball throw, came to the conclusion that the optimal angle of the ball ejection depends on the individual characteristics of the athlete. The higher the athlete's ability to differentiate the speed of the ball, the more gentle the trajectory of the ball it is advisable for him to choose. On the contrary, athletes who differentiate the direction of the throw well can be recommended to perform throws with a hinged trajectory.

To determine the effectiveness of basketball players during the game, a number of authors suggest calculating the positive actions of each player (picking up the ball on his shield and the opponent's shield, interception and assists), negative actions (personal mistakes, ball losses during transfers and technical errors), as well as the effectiveness during the time on the court. F. Lindberg,

The main phase: the player jumps out with a push with two legs, while the torso is turned directly to the ring, the legs are slightly bent.

When reaching the highest point of the jump, the player directs the ball into the basket by straightening his right hand forward-up and with an energetic but smooth movement of the hand and fingers. The ball is given a reverse rotation. The left hand is removed from the ball at the moment of the beginning of the movement of the right hand. The distance from the place of separation from the platform to the place of landing of the player after the throw should not be minimal and should not exceed 25-30 cm, which allows him to avoid a collision with a defender.

When performing a jump throw from a relatively close distance, there is no need for a large amplitude of extension of the arm with the ball. The main throwing movement is the movement of the hand and finger, which increases the

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level of the initial position of the ball immediately before the throw and the point of release of the ball - then the player can successfully overcome the opponent's resistance.

A throw in a jump with a deviation of the trunk back began to be used to attack the ring from close and medium distances with the dense tutelage of a tall defender with good jumping ability. The ball is released over the head out of the player's central field of view - it flies along a hinged trajectory, which to a certain extent makes it difficult to achieve high accuracy of the throw.

Throwing the ball into the basket in a jump is usually performed under highly varying conditions with diverse effects on the player, the main of which are the actions of opponents. A modern higher school should not only reflect, but to a certain extent outstrip the achievements of practice, provide future specialists with certain qualifications and mastering the methodology of "permanent acquisition of knowledge" throughout their work. This is connected with the shift of emphasis from the informational method of teaching to the methodological one, with the instilling in students the skills of independent acquisition of knowledge.

This provision is also fundamentally important for the compulsory academic discipline of universities "Physical Culture". It indicates the need to strengthen the educational orientation in it, increase the share of independent studies.

Physical development is the process of formation and change of morphofunctional properties of the organism, physical qualities and abilities, which is carried out under the influence of living conditions and upbringing during the individual life of a person and from generation to generation.

During the period of study at a higher educational institution, the abilities and inclinations of students are revealed, the most active development of moral and aesthetic qualities takes place, the formation and stabilization of character, interests; sensory-perceptual, psychomotor functions develop; the greatest plasticity and learnability in the formation of skills is observed; mainly somatic and psychophysical development reaches an optimum. All this emphasizes, on the one hand, the availability of potential opportunities for students, and on the other, the need to maximize the realization of these opportunities in the learning process.

The formation of a person's needs for motor activity, the creation of motivational attitudes, assistance in choosing forms of classes for the full self-realization of the individual is the meaning of physical education. At the present stage of society's development, it is necessary to lay methodological and value-humanistic foundations for the formation of a true physical culture in a student.

Physical culture as a system is a unity of specific physical culture needs, relationships, etc. The disclosure of these aspects in the system of physical culture from the standpoint of a humanistic approach to personality formation makes it possible to convey to the younger generation the true content of physical culture as part of universal culture.

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As a social phenomenon, it should, first of all, contribute to the formation of individual physical culture. One of the most complete definitions of physical culture is given by L.P. Matveyev. He believes that physical culture is a set of achievements of society in the creation of special means, methods and conditions for the directed development of physical capacity of the younger and adult generations, one of the effective means of comprehensive harmonious development of personality, an effective social factor in the movement of each person along the path of physical improvement.

Among the main criteria for the formation of physical culture of university students, it is necessary to single out objective (the requirements of society in the training of specialists) and subjective (personal desire, goals, motivation) opportunities of a young person in the implementation of a multifaceted physical activity.

The priority components of the formation of physical culture of the individual and its immediate components are awareness of knowledge in this field of activity, the needs, motives and goals of the student's personality. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the aspect of humanity, reflecting the modern direction of humanitarization of the educational process.

The formation of a student's personality is also self-realization, self-expression of his human essence, the unity of the natural foundations of socially significant qualities acquired in the process of studying. Inadequate (overestimated or underestimated) self-esteem, as well as unstable self-esteem deform the inner world of the individual, distort

her motivation and emotional-volitional sphere, and this hinders the harmonious development of personality, mental and social health. A high degree of coincidence corresponds to good mental health. Self-esteem depends on the extent to which a person feels belonging to a significant social group for him. In the future by with the accumulation of experience, the evaluation of the results of one's own activities begins to become increasingly important. Formed, i.e. adequate, differentiated, conscious self-esteem to a certain extent is freed from the assessments of others, becomes an independent result of human behavior. According to the statements of K. Rogers, a high, "looking ahead" self-assessment of real opportunities is necessary for the personal growth of each person.

One of the most important goals of physical culture and sports is to educate those engaged in an active life position characterized by patriotism, high morality and citizenship. National sports and folk games, which include all the main types of movements and develop a wide range of skills, including professional ones, are of great lasting value as a means of not only physical, but also spiritual and moral education. Their classes foster people's respect for the cultural traditions of different peoples.

Physical culture and sports have great opportunities in returning disabled people to a full-fledged physical and spiritual life. An example is L.E. Sergeev, V.I. Dikul, and others. L.E. Sergeev, who lost his foot at the front, returned to

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work in geological expeditions thanks to the strong-willed hardening received in his youth during swimming, rowing, horseback riding, mountaineering. Honored Artist, cirka worker V.I. Dikul suffered a spinal injury, falling from a height of 13 m, after then he was bedridden for five years. Outstanding willpower, self-discipline, purposefulness, educated and developed in the course of acrobatics and other sports, allowed him to return to the circus again. V.I. Dikul created his own system of rehabilitation of disabled people with spinal injuries and successfully applies it in practice.

As a result of the profound socio-economic and political changes taking place, physical culture and sport have become a global cultural and social phenomenon. The scale of this development is evidenced by the formation of national and regional unions and associations, international sports federations, the holding of national and regional international championships, the registration of competitions in various sports and disciplines, the Olympic Games, as well as the mass dissemination of physical culture and sports in various social systems.

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